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Identification of self-citations in Google Scholar author profiles¹

Alberto Martín-Martín*, Juan María Fernández-Pérez* and Emilio Delgado López-Cózar*

* albertomartin@ugr.es; juanmaf@go.ugr.es; edelgado@ugr.es

Facultad de Comunicación y Documentación, Universidad de Granada, Colegio Máximo de Cartuja, Campus de Cartuja s/n, Granada, 18011 (Spain)

Introduction

Researcher profile platforms are increasingly being used to showcase the publication history of academic authors and the impact of their publications, measured through a variety of bibliometric indicators. These profiles are sometimes used, formally or informally, in researcher evaluations, and for this reason it is important to understand what they offer.

Some author profile platforms, such as the ones in ResearchGate and Academia.edu, are part of academic social networks, while others derive from bibliographic databases or search engines: Publons integrates data from Web of Science and will soon be fully integrated into this platform, the Scopus Author ID is a part of the Scopus database, and Google Scholar author profiles directly feed off Google Scholar data. In this work, we will focus on Google Scholar author profiles.

Google Scholar is currently one of the most widely used literature discovery services (Blankstein & Wolff-Eisenberg, 2019). One of the characteristics that sets it apart from similar tools is that, unlike other citation indexes such as Web of Science and Scopus, which implement selective and supervised document indexing criteria, Google Scholar applies an inclusive and unsupervised method to identify and index academic documents. They accomplish this by regularly parsing the academic web, in a similar manner to general purpose search engines. Through this method, Google Scholar identifies a significantly larger collection of academic documents when compared to other bibliographic databases (Martín-Martín et al., 2021), at the cost of data quality and other errors (Martín-Martín & Delgado López-Cózar, 2021; Orduna-Malea et al., 2017).

Google Scholar author profiles are also widely used. A survey from 2015-2016 showed Google Scholar profiles as the most popular option among researcher profiles (Bosman & Kramer, 2016)). An update several years later, however, showed that ResearchGate profiles had surpassed Google Scholar, and this difference might have increased in the last few years

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(Kramer & Bosman, 2018). A list of researchers in Spain with public Google Scholar profiles that has been updated over the years has seen a large increase in the number of profiles: from approximately 55,000 in 2018, to over 100,000 at the end of 2021 (Aguillo, 2018, 2021).

In a Google Scholar profile, researchers are able to compile a list of all the publications they have authored and which are covered by Google Scholar. Additionally, the profile uses the list of documents included in the profile to generate several bibliometric indicators: sum of citations received, h index, and i10-index (number of publications with at least 10 citations). There is no external control over which publications are added to the profile, and it is easy for authors to manipulate their bibliometric indicators by uploading documents that cite their publications to personal websites, repositories, or academic social network sites (Chawla, 2022; Delgado López-Cózar et al., 2014). Furthermore, by default, profiles are set to update automatically, which means that Google Scholar decides whether to include new publications in the profile based on similarity of author names. This usually leads to the inclusion of misattributed documents in profile, especially when the author has common surnames.

The potential errors and manipulations that might be present in Google Scholar profiles are sometimes not easily identifiable by users who visit the profiles. Furthermore, some users might be interested in exploring the data available in the profile in ways that are not supported by the native interface, or in calculating a different set of indicators than those provided in the profile page. For this reason, the development of procedures that facilitate these tasks would be useful in cases where the comprehensiveness of Google Scholar's coverage is considered necessary, but the data presented in the profile is not enough. The software *Publish or Perish* (Harzing, 2007) facilitates some of these tasks.

As a first step in a larger project in which our goal is to expand the range of options available to users of Google Scholar profiles, this study describes how data from Google Scholar profiles and Google Scholar results pages can be used to identify self-citations, which are not natively identified by the platform (Sandnes, 2020).

Self-citations have been a topic of interest in scientometrics for decades (Tagliacozzo, 1977). They are a natural byproduct of authors working in the same research lines over time, although some studies report cases of extreme self-citation, which could be attempts to inflate bibliometric indicators (Van Noorden & Singh Chawla, 2019). Because of this there is a discussion regarding how self-citations should be processed when calculating impact indicators at the individual level, with several proposals in favour of visibilizing this information rather than deciding to simply include or exclude self-citations from computations (Flatt et al., 2017; Kacem et al., 2020).

In line with these proposals, the main objective of this paper is to develop and describe an automated method to identify self-citations at the document and author levels, using data from Google Scholar profiles, and test it using a single profile as a case study.

Methods

Because Google Scholar does not facilitate data extraction (Else, 2018) our approach relies on web scraping techniques. When Google Scholar requests CAPTCHAs, the scrapers pause and a person must solve the CAPTCHA before being able to continue. A collection of scrapers was developed using the R programming language. The scrapers function as follows (Figure 1):

1. Once a public profile is selected, the scraper loads the complete list of publications in the profile (by default, only the top 20 most cited publications are displayed). Then the HTML code is downloaded to the local machine.
2. The scraper parses the local HTML copy of the profile, and generates a table of publications. The link that is behind the number of citations of each publication contains one or several IDs that identify the cited document (Figure 2). The appearance of several IDs indicate that the author has manually merged several versions of the same document which Google Scholar has not identified as the same document. These IDs are extracted as input for the next phase.
3. The IDs of the cited documents are used to iteratively navigate to the list of citing documents of each document in the profile. These lists of citing documents are downloaded as raw HTML.
4. A scraper processes the local HTMLs that contain lists of citing documents, and saves them to a table. This table also contains the IDs of the citing documents, as well as, in some cases, the profile IDs of some authors of the citing documents.
5. Author self-citations (self-citations from documents authored by the same researcher we are analysing) can be identified by comparing the IDs of the documents available in the profile, with the IDs of the citing documents (Figure 2). A limitation of this step is that the document ID of the citing document is sometimes not publicly exposed in Google Scholar results pages. This is the case when the citing document itself has not received any citations, and at the same time, Google Scholar has not been able to find more than one version of the document online (the ID is embedded in the Cited by link, and the Versions link).
6. Self-citations were also identified using the author profile ID that is sometimes available in the list of authors within citing documents, to test potential discrepancies and find author self-citations that could not be found using step 5.

Figure 1: Flow of data during the web scraping and self-citation calculation process

Figure 2: Identification of self-citations via document IDs

The figure shows a Google Scholar profile for Emilio Delgado López-Cózar. The profile includes a photo, name, affiliation (Universidad de Granada), and a list of publications. A table on the right shows citation statistics: Citas (6728), Índice h (43), Índice i10 (133), and a total of 920 citations since 2015. A specific publication from 2003 is highlighted with a downward arrow pointing to a search result for the same title. The search result shows it is cited by 71 articles. A URL is shown with the document ID 17318596058626149865 highlighted in yellow. A green checkmark is placed above this ID. A second URL is shown below, also with the same ID highlighted in yellow. An upward arrow points from this ID to a search result for a 2010 publication, which is cited by 77 articles. A text box in the center explains the process: 'Al buscar coincidencias entre los códigos de los documentos citantes y los códigos de los documentos del perfil, se ha podido verificar que uno de los documentos que se encuentran entre los que citan al primero, es a su vez, otro de los documentos perteneciente a éste autor.'

A limitation of this process is that it is not able to identify cases in which a self-citation is generated by co-authors of the researcher we are analysing, in publications where our focus researcher does not participate (from now on, co-author self-citations).

In order to test the effectiveness of this approach to identifying self-citations in Google Scholar profiles, we applied our scripts to the profile of professor Emilio Delgado López-Cózar. Data was extracted in June 2020. After applying this procedure, we manually checked citations to identify the self-citations that the scripts were not able to find (especially co-author self-citations).

The used in the calculations will be released upon publication.

Results

The profile used in this case study contained 415 publications which had received 6,818 citations according to Google Scholar at the time of data collection. Our script detected 675 author self-citations (9.9% of all citations received). Of these 443 self-citations were found by matching the author profile ID, and 596 self-citations were found by matching the IDs of citing documents and the documents available in the profile (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Percentage of self-citations identified by the script

After manually checking the list of citations, an additional 194 self-citations were identified. Most of these (176) were co-author self-citations (which our method is not able to detect yet), while 18 were author self-citations that our algorithm was not able to detect either through document ID matching, or author profile ID matching. In all these cases, the reason was that document ID matching was not possible because the ID of the citing document was not exposed, and author profile ID matching was not possible because the researcher was last author, and his name was not exposed in the list of author names of the citing document (Google Scholar routinely truncates author names in results pages). These 194 additional self-citations make up 2.8% of all citations received by the author, raising the total self-citation rate to 12.7%. Our scripts were able to identify 77.6% of all self-citations in the profile, while 22.4% of self-citations could only be identified manually (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Percentage of self-citations identified by the script

Using this information, it is possible replicate the citation bar graph displayed by Google Scholar, visibilizing self-citations as suggested by Kacem et al. (2020) (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Percentage of self-citations identified by the script

Discussion and conclusions

In this study we only apply the script to one profile. Therefore the results of the analysis regarding the efficacy of the scripts to detect all self-citations are not generalizable. These results provide, however, some useful information that can help us improve the script in the future.

Most of the self-citations that are not detected by the script are co-author self-citations, which we knew the script could not detect. For these cases, several approaches could be followed in the future:

- If the profile of our focus author includes a list of co-authors (Figure 6), the list of documents in the profile of each co-author could be downloaded, and then document IDs could be compared.
- Author lists in the list of publications of our focus author could be compared with author lists in the citing publications. The limitation with this approach is that author names are not standardised in Google Scholar, and that author lists are often incomplete in Google Scholar results pages.

Figure 6: Identification of co-author self-citations

Emilio Delgado López-Cózar
 Professor Research Methods, Facultad de Comunicación y Documentación, Universidad de Granada
 Dirección de correo verificada de ugr.es - [Página principal](#)
 Scholarly communication Research Evaluation Bibliometrics Scientometrics Altmetrics

Coautores VER TODOS

- Rafael Ruiz-Perez
- Enrique Orduña-Malea
- Daniel Torres-Salinas
- Alberto Martín-Martín
- Evaristo Jimenez-Contreras**

TÍTULO CITADO POR AÑO

The evolution of research activity in Spain: The impact of the National Commission for the Evaluation of Research Activity (CNEAI)
 E Jiménez Contreras, F Moya Anegón, E Delgado López-Cózar
 Research Policy 32 (1), 123-142 304 2003

Enlace a Documentos citantes

Cita de Co-autor
 La aportación española a la producción científica internacional en bibliotecología y documentación: balance de diez años (1992-2001)
 E Jiménez-Contreras - EID: textos universitaris de bibliotecologia i ..., 2002 - eprints.rciis.org
 Se presenta un análisis de las publicaciones de los investigadores españoles del ámbito de la Bibliotecología y Documentación (ByD) que han sido difundidas a través de revistas internacionales, entendiéndose por tales las que son recogidas por las bases de datos del ...
 ☆ Citado por 55 Artículos relacionados Las 7 versiones

If we compare the self-citation rate computed using Google Scholar for the author in this study (9.9% if we consider only author self-citations, and 12.7% if we also consider co-author self-citations) and compare it with those available in other data sources, the results are quite similar. In Web of Science, the author had received a total of 1,517 citations at the same time that the data for this study was collected, 1,380 excluding self-citations, resulting in a self-citation rate of 9.03% (Web of Science only computes author self-citations when using its citation report functionality). In Scopus, the author had received a total of 1,554 citations, 1,410 excluding author self-citations (9.3%), and 1,318 excluding co-author self-citations as well (15,18%). Future studies could test whether these similarities hold in large samples of author profiles.

References

- Aguillo, I. F. (2018). *Ranking of scientists in Spain [June 2018]*. <https://web.archive.org/web/20180703150025/https://www.webometrics.info/en/GoogleScholar/Spain>
- Aguillo, I. F. (2021). *Ranking of researchers in Spain and Spaniards abroad [December 2021]*. <https://web.archive.org/web/20220415075008/https://www.webometrics.info/en/GoogleScholar/Spain>
- Blankstein, M., & Wolff-Eisenberg, C. (2019). *Ithaka S+R US Faculty Survey 2018*. Ithaka S+R. <https://doi.org/10.18665/sr.311199>
- Bosman, J., & Kramer, B. (2016). *Innovations in scholarly communication—Data of the global 2015-2016 survey*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.49583>
- Chawla, A. D. S. (2022, March 25). How critics say a computer scientist in Spain artificially boosted his Google Scholar metrics. *Retraction Watch*. <https://retractionwatch.com/2022/03/25/how-critics-say-a-computer-scientist-in-spain-artificially-boosted-his-google-scholar-metrics/>
- Delgado López-Cózar, E., Robinson-García, N., & Torres-Salinas, D. (2014). The Google scholar experiment: How to index false papers and manipulate bibliometric indicators. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 65(3), 446–454. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23056>
- Else, H. (2018, April 11). How I scraped data from Google Scholar. *Nature*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-018-04190-5>
- Flatt, J. W., Blasimme, A., & Vayena, E. (2017). Improving the Measurement of Scientific Success by Reporting a Self-Citation Index. *Publications*, 5(3), 20. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications5030020>
- Harzing, A. W. (2007). *Publish or Perish*. <https://harzing.com/resources/publish-or-perish>
- Kacem, A., Flatt, J. W., & Mayr, P. (2020). Tracking self-citations in academic publishing. *Scientometrics*, 123(2), 1157–1165. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-020-03413-9>
- Kramer, B., & Bosman, J. (2018, August 15). *Researcher profiles*. Innovations in Scholarly Communication. <https://101innovations.wordpress.com/survey-results/research-activities/profiles/>

- Martín-Martín, A., & Delgado López-Cózar, E. (2021, July 12). Large coverage fluctuations in Google Scholar: A case study. *18th International Conference on Scientometrics & Informetrics*. <http://arxiv.org/abs/2102.07571>
- Martín-Martín, A., Thelwall, M., Orduna-Malea, E., & Delgado López-Cózar, E. (2021). Google Scholar, Microsoft Academic, Scopus, Dimensions, Web of Science, and OpenCitations' COCI: A multidisciplinary comparison of coverage via citations. *Scientometrics*, *126*(1), 871–906. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-020-03690-4>
- Orduna-Malea, E., Martín-Martín, A., & Delgado López-Cózar, E. (2017). Google Scholar as a source for scholarly evaluation: A bibliographic review of database errors. *Revista Española de Documentación Científica*, *40*(4), e185. <https://doi.org/10.3989/redc.2017.4.1500>
- Sandnes, F. E. (2020). A simple back-of-the-envelope test for self-citations using Google Scholar author profiles. *Scientometrics*, *124*(2), 1685–1689. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-020-03521-6>
- Tagliacozzo, R. (1977). Self-citations in scientific literature. *Journal of Documentation*, *33*(4), 251–265. <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb026644>
- Van Noorden, R., & Singh Chawla, D. (2019). Hundreds of extreme self-citing scientists revealed in new database. *Nature*, *572*(7771), 578–579. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-019-02479-7>